

Stakeholder Synergy In The Management of Embung Banteran Tourism, Sumbang District

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ABSTRACT: The Asih Swargaloka Embung Tanggul Tourism, located in Banteran Village, Sumbang District, Banyumas Regency, has experienced a decrease in the number of visitors and the condition of unmaintained facilities since it was inaugurated in July 2023. This study aims to identify the factors causing the decline and develop development strategies that can increase the attractiveness of this tourism. This study uses a descriptive qualitative method. The location of the research is in Banteran Village, Sumbang District, Banyumas Regency. The data collection technique was carried out through in-depth interviews with each stakeholder as a tourist village manager. The results of interviews with resource persons revealed that expensive entrance ticket prices, lack of promotions, and poor facility conditions were the main factors in the decline in visitors. In addition, the lack of synergy between the village government, investors, and the local community also hinders the development of this tourism. To overcome this problem, several strategic steps are recommended, including reducing entrance ticket prices, improving and adding facilities, increasing promotion through various media, and training to increase the capacity of tourism village managers. In addition, a participatory approach that involves the community in tourism management and development is expected to increase the community's sense of ownership and responsibility. The implementation of a comprehensive development strategy and good synergy between all stakeholders is expected to restore the attractiveness of the Asih Swargaloka Embung Embankment Tourism and make it a sustainable source of income for Banteran Village. Training, empowerment of tourism village managers, facility improvements, and effective promotion will be the key to the success of this tourism development.

KEYWORDS: Synergy, Role, Stakeholders, Tourism Village, Tourism

1. INTRODUCTION

Today, the tourism sector in Indonesia is one of the main foreign exchange contributors for a promising country. This can be seen from data released by the Central Statistics Agency (BPS) from January to September 2023, foreign tourist visits in Indonesia increased by 143.41 percent compared to 2022. Meanwhile, Indonesian tourists or foreign tourists also experienced an increase of 13.36 percent compared to last year (Badan Pusat Statistik, 2023). To continue to encourage the country's economy from the tourism industry sector, the Ministry of Tourism and Creative Economy is intensively developing one of them through the development of tourist villages.

A tourist village is a village that has good potential in terms of society, nature and culture as a unique and interesting thing (Sudibya, 2018). This uniqueness is used as a strategy to increase Indonesia's tourism. The development of tourism-based villages is one of the community's innovations in capturing tourism opportunities and potentials in the village, so that it will increase community productivity. Not only that, the existence of tourist villages also has an impact on increasing village income. This is in line with what was conveyed by Indriyani, et al. (Suranny, 2020) that the existence of a tourist village that is well developed by the village government and the community will be a source of income for the village and the community. With good management or development, it can also have a positive impact such as creating jobs for the community, maintaining the culture or traditions that exist in the local village, encouraging the development of small and medium industries managed by the local community and can be a means of promoting local products (Suranny, 2020).

Banyumas is one of the areas in Central Java province where most of the area is rural, where each village has the potential to be developed into a tourist village (Kurniawan et al., 2023). One of the villages in Banyumas Regency that is trying to develop its tourism potential is Banteran Village, Sumbang District. Banteran Village has an area of 363,785 hectares with a population of 9,225 people. A village located quite far from the city center but on the eastern Baturraden tourist trail. The village has an artificial reservoir in the middle of a stretch of rice fields with a capacity of 21,000 m³. The reservoir was originally used to

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irrigate agricultural land, now it has developed into a tourist attraction called Embung Tanggul Asih Swargaloka Tourism which was just inaugurated in mid-July 2023. With the cooperation of stakeholders consisting of the village government and investors, the tourist attraction has a variety of facilities such as restaurants, lodgings and a line of MSME product stalls.

Embung tourism is the only tourist attraction in the village and is being developed to increase the village's original income and develop Banteran village as a tourist village. However, based on initial observations in the field at this time, the tourist attraction has experienced a decrease in the number of visitors. According to the secretary of the Banteran village government, Slamet Riyanto said that the decline was indicated because of the absence of innovation or development of facilities provided at tourist attractions, so that visitors felt bored and reluctant to return to tourist attractions. So the question arises about how the synergy of stakeholders as the manager of the Embung Tanggul Asih Swargaloka Banteran tourist attraction? This is because the lack of synergy of stakeholders can hinder the development of tourist attractions, resulting in a decrease in the number of visitors. So that this study aims to examine the extent of synergy among stakeholders including the village government, investors and local communities in the management of the Asih Swargaloka Embung Tanggul Banteran tourism.

This research is supported by several previous studies, one of which is entitled "Stakeholder Synergy in Realizing Tourism Activities in Baha Tourism Village, Mengwi District, Badung Regency" by Haryanti and Nugroho (2018). The similarity with this research is in terms of the purpose of the research, namely to examine the synergy of tourism village stakeholders. As a result, it was found that there was an inconsistency in terms of the implementation of obligations and rights of each stakeholder so that it stagnated (Haryanti & Nugroho, 2018). Meanwhile, the difference lies in the object of the research, where this research uses a tourist attraction in Banyumas Regency, namely Banteran Village.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Tourism Village Concept

Tourism villages are tourism assets whose development is based on the potential that exists in the village. The potential they have is a special attraction such as society, nature, and culture. This potential is also part of the identity of the village (Sudibya, 2018). In line with Lestari, et.al (2023) which states that a tourist village is a village condition that offers an authentic atmosphere of rural origin such as customs, daily life, socio-culture, history, building architecture, and so on that have their own characteristics and uniqueness (Lestari et al., 2023). Meanwhile, referring to the Final Report of the Village Development Study in Yogyakarta in 2014, it defines a tourist village as a form of integration between attractions. Accommodation and supporting facilities presented in a community life structure that is integrated with applicable ordinances and traditions. (Sudibya, 2018)

To become a tourist village, there are criteria that are determined such as easy road access, having interesting objects in the form of nature, cultural arts, legends, local food and so on. The next criteria are the community and village officials who fully support tourist attractions, guaranteed security, the availability of adequate accommodation, telecommunications and labor, and a cool climate (Hadiwijoyo, 2012).

Tourism villages provide opportunities for village communities to become the main actors in the tourism industry. They can manage homestays, become tour guides, sell local products, and provide direct services to tourists (Rifansyah & Sihombing, 2022). This increases the income and welfare of the local community. Through tourist villages, local culture and the natural environment of the village can be further preserved (Pratiwi et al., 2022). Awareness of the importance of preserving culture and nature is higher because both are the main assets in attracting tourists. Tourism villages help diversify village income sources, not only depending on the agricultural or fishery sectors (Kurniawan et al., 2023). Tourism is a new economic sector that can reduce people's dependence on traditional sectors. The development of tourist villages is often followed by an improvement in infrastructure, such as roads, transportation, and public facilities. This is not only beneficial for tourists but also for the village community in daily life. (Rahayu et al., 2023; Pious et al., 2023)

2.2 Stakeholder Role

Murphy and Murphy (2004) said that stakeholders are those who have the power and right to participate in decision-making, as well as those who give and/or are affected by the outcome of the decision. They can be men or women, communities, social groups, or institutions (Murphy & Murphy, 2004). Stakeholders can be divided into three groups, namely the government, business/private actors and local communities. The three groups have their respective roles such as the government as a regulator and facilitator, business/private actors as supporters as well as capital owners, and local communities as parties who receive and interact directly with visitors (Pitana & Gayatri, 2005).

In more detail, the role of stakeholders is as policy creators, coordinators, facilitators, implementers, and accelerators. The policy creator in question is the role of making decisions and determining a policy. The government, especially local governments, has an important role as a policy maker that will affect the course of the tourist village project. They are responsible for formulating regulations, policies, and regulations that support the development of tourist villages, such as zoning regulations, business licenses, and operational standards. Policies made by the government can determine the direction of tourism village development and ensure that all activities carried out are in accordance with the law and the public interest.

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Then the role of the coordinator is to coordinate between stakeholders involved in management. Furthermore, the role of the facilitator is to meet the needs of the object. In addition, there is also the role of the implementer which plays a role in implementing existing policies on tourist attractions, as well as the role of accelerators such as contributing and determining the time so that the program is carried out right and quickly according to the target (H. C. Nugroho et al., 2014). Investors play the role of accelerators that encourage the acceleration of the development of tourist villages. They have the ability to accelerate the process of building and operationalizing projects through the right investments and effective business strategies. With this role, investors can help tourism villages achieve development targets faster and with better results (A. Y. Nugroho et al., 2022)

The local community is the main stakeholder in the development of tourist villages, because they are the direct implementers of many activities that occur in tourist villages. They act as implementers who carry out various daily activities that support the operation of tourist villages, such as managing homestays, providing tour guide services, selling local products, and managing tourist facilities. This role is very important because the success of a tourist village is highly dependent on the active involvement and support of the local community (Margayaningsih, 2019).

Stakeholders play a very important role in the success of a project or program, including in the context of tourism village development. A stakeholder is an individual, group, or organization that has a specific interest or role in a project and can influence or be influenced by the outcome of the project. Each stakeholder has different responsibilities and contributions, all of which must be harmonized to achieve common goals (Ciptaningsih & Nurcahyanto, 2019; Khomzi et al., 2020)

2.3 Stakeholder Synergy

Communication between the three stakeholder groups requires synergy. Synergy comes from the word synergy which, according to the Great Dictionary of the Indonesian Language (KBBI), means joint activities. Synergy can also be interpreted as a combination or guide of elements or parts that can produce better and greater output (Najiyati & Susilo, 2011). The combination is carried out by several parties or related parts. According to Richard L. Draft, the interaction carried out by several parts of an organization to create a greater impact than just individuality is called synergy. Thus, stakeholder synergy (in the Manggalou, 2022) related to the management of tourism villages can be concluded as an interaction carried out by stakeholders which in this case consists of the government, business actors/private sector and local communities to produce greater outputs/impacts.

Najiyati and Susilo (2011) said that to build synergy, there are two ways, namely through communication and coordination. These two things are interconnected (Najiyati & Susilo, 2011). Communication itself can be done through vertical communication (up/down communication) and horizontal communication (equal/peer-to-peer). Meanwhile, coordination is carried out to integrate individual activities into one joint effort to achieve common goals (Silalahi, 2011). These two ways can encourage the creation of synergy from stakeholders in the management of tourism villages. Clear, transparent, and regular communication between all stakeholders is very important. This allows each party to understand their respective roles and responsibilities, share relevant information, and resolve issues collaboratively (Pintossi et al., 2023).

Stakeholder synergy is a process in which various parties who have an interest in a project or program collaborate in a mutually beneficial way, to achieve goals that cannot be achieved optimally if done individually (Berliandaldo et al., 2021). This synergy not only includes technical and operational cooperation, but also includes strategic aspects, such as planning, decision-making, and evaluation. In synergy, each stakeholder brings its unique strengths into the partnership. When all these elements work synergistically, they create a greater effect than if they worked separately (Liu & Kou, 2024). By building harmonious and effective cooperation between all stakeholders, common goals can be achieved more efficiently, sustainably, and provide broad benefits for all parties involved. Although there are challenges in achieving synergy, with good communication, trust, and commitment to a common goal, synergy can be achieved and bring significant results (Setiawan et al., 2023)

3. RESEARCH METHODS

This research uses a qualitative research method, namely research that produces descriptive data in the form of written and oral words, especially this research will also have many questions that try to explore the elements of how. In accordance with the formulation of the problem, this research will be carried out in Banteran Village, Sumbang District, Banyumas Regency. Then, the technique of taking informants will be carried out through the purposive sampling technique, which is to deliberately select informants who meet the specified criteria, namely the manager of the Banteran tourist village. The managers are stakeholders consisting of village governments, private actors/investors and local communities. As for the data collection technique, it will be carried out through in-depth interviews with each stakeholder as the manager of the tourist village. This study uses data analysis of an interactive model from Miles, Huberman and Saldana (2014) which consists of data condensation, data presentation and conclusion drawn (Miles et al., 2014). Meanwhile, the validity of the data uses source triangulation, namely by exploring the truth of the data through various data sources.

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4. RESULT

4.1 History and Early Conditions

In early 2022, Banteran Village built a reservoir with an area of 0.5 ha and a capacity of 21,000 m³. The reservoir was built to be a source of irrigation water for the surrounding rice fields. Then, in mid-July 2023, it will be developed into a tourist attraction named Embung Tanggul Asih Swargaloka. It is located in the northern part of Banteran village, Sumbang District, Banyumas Regency, precisely on the border between Banteran village and Gandatapa village. The development of this tourist attraction is based on the hope of Banteran Village to become a tourist village with its natural potential.

Figure 1. Banteran Reservoir in 2022

Source: Instagram @purwokertohealing

The construction of the reservoir into a tourist attraction was carried out by stakeholders consisting of the Banteran Village Government and investors. The village plays the role of land owner, supervisor and policy holder, while the investor plays the role of field management and main fund support.

During the initial construction, as a prospective tourist attraction, Embung did not enforce an entrance ticket so that it was crowded with local tourists. This is also one of the village's promotional strategies to introduce Embung Banteran. The facilities available during the promotion consist of electric bicycle rentals around the embankment, trampoline rides and painting. The facility is provided by the village by opening cooperation with facility providers to attract visitors.

When the Embung was inaugurated, it should be a tourist attraction, an entrance ticket of Rp 10,000 was imposed for each visitor. The stakeholder policy, which consists of several investors and the village government, did not run for long because according to the Head of Banteran Village, Eddi Suhedi, the nominal amount of the ticket was considered too expensive for local visitors who incidentally lived in rural areas. This is evidenced by the decrease in the number of visitors to the Embung Tanggul Asih Swargaloka tourist attraction. This is also supported by the statement of one of the stall traders at the tourist attraction if the Embung Tanggul Asih Swargaloka experienced a crowd of visitors in the first three months after it was inaugurated. The village government as the policy holder and supervisor asked the investor to reduce the entrance ticket price to Rp 2,000 in order to attract the interest of visitors who at that time were still dominant from the surrounding Banteran area. The request was approved by investors.

As a tourist attraction, Embung has a variety of interesting rides as well as natural scenery with Mount Slamet in the background which is an attraction for local and foreign tourists to visit. Some of the rides that can be enjoyed when visiting this Embung tour include water bikes, ATVs, electric bikes, outbound rides, camp areas and children's playgrounds. The facilities provided include restaurants, MSME product stalls, lodging/cottages, and spacious parikir places. These facilities have their own rent/use fees outside of the entrance fee. Like ATVs that can be enjoyed with a rental fee of Rp 10,000 for two trips around the pond area. Cottage rental for one day and one night is IDR 300,000 to IDR 500,000 depending on the completeness of facilities such as air conditioning, wifi, and others.

Figure 2. Embung Tourist Attraction Facilities

Source: Researcher Documentation, 2024

4.2 Current Conditions

Currently, Embung Tourism has experienced a decrease in the number of visitors even though the entrance ticket price has been free. As a result, many stalls and facilities are closed. According to one of the traders who rented the stalls, only three stalls and one restaurant are still operating to date. Meanwhile, other stalls are closed because they do not generate income to cover rental costs. Some of the existing facilities are also not well maintained, for example damaged water bike rides, some cottages that are not maintained, and camp areas that are also not well managed. This condition makes tourist attractions less attractive to new visitors.

Figure 3. Asih Swargaloka Embankment Facilities Today

Source: Researcher Documentation, 2024

The stall owner, who is indirectly one of the stakeholders because it is a local community that also has an interest in it, said that the number of visitors who have experienced a very drastic decline has harmed the stall owners because of the lack of income. Meanwhile, they have paid the rent to the investor as the field management at the beginning of the lease. The price of renting a kiosk at Wisata Embung ranges from IDR 7,500,000 to IDR 30,000,000 per year depending on the location of the kiosk chosen. The more strategic and spacious, the higher the rental price. This amount is expensive for kiosk tenants in new tourist attractions located in the countryside.

The cause of the decrease in the number of visitors is not only due to the expensive ticket price, but also promotional efforts from the management that are considered inadequate. Wisata Embung has an Instagram social media account named @embung_banteran_sumbang which was last active in December 2023. Even so, some rides and facilities are still actively promoting their businesses through their own social media accounts because they are managed by investors who are different from the investors who manage Embung as a whole. The resource person also gave suggestions that the entrance ticket be free or at least the ticket fee is reduced and only a parking fee is charged to attract visitors. According to him, the cost of parking a motorbike of Rp 3,000 to Rp 5,000 is more reasonable compared to the high entrance fee. In addition, the resource person also proposed that managers be more aggressive in promoting and improving existing facilities.

Figure 4. Embung Banteran Tourism Rating

Source: Google

5. DISCUSSION

Stakeholders are a combination of several people or agencies who have an interest in building a program together. In its implementation, the combination (Elista et al., 2020) of stakeholders has several roles, namely as policy creators, coordinators, facilitators, implementers and accelerators (H. C. Nugroho et al., 2014). The Asih Swargaloka Embankment as a tourist attraction has stakeholders consisting of the Banteran Village Government, investors and local communities such as stall owners and parking attendants. Stakeholder synergy is an important aspect in the development of tourist attractions such as the Asih Swargaloka Embankment. When stakeholders, consisting of village governments, investors, and local communities, work together in harmony, tourism development can be carried out effectively and sustainably.

Each stakeholder has different interests and goals in a project. Synergy allows all parties to align their goals and work together to achieve the desired outcome more effectively (Berliandaldo et al., 2021). When stakeholders work in harmony, resources can be optimized, decisions can be made more wisely, and common goals can be achieved more quickly. In the development of tourism or other projects, resources such as funds, manpower, and information are often limited. With synergy, stakeholders can share resources with each other and utilize the strengths of each party to overcome these limitations (Rahmadi, 2021). When various parties with different backgrounds, expertise, and perspectives work together, opportunities for innovation and creativity increase (Ingkadijaya & Bilqis, 2020). Stakeholder synergy allows for a richer and more diverse exchange of ideas, which can lead to new and better solutions to the challenges faced in project development. One of the main benefits of stakeholder synergy is increased participation and a sense of ownership by local communities in the project. When people are involved in the decision-making process and project execution, they feel part of the project and have a responsibility to ensure its success. This participation not only increases the effectiveness of project implementation, but also strengthens the relationship between the community and other stakeholders, such as the government and investors (Khomzi et al., 2020; A. Y. Nugroho et al., 2022).

In the development of the Embung Banteran tourist attraction, the Village Government plays the role of a policy creator, namely as a decision-maker and policy maker. For example, the reduction in the price of entrance tickets to the Embung tourist attraction, decided by the Village Government from the price of Rp 10,000 to Rp 2,000 and even now it is free to attract visitors. In addition, the Village Government is also a coordinator because it coordinates with other stakeholders. Such as holding a meeting to discuss the development of tourist attractions. Meanwhile, investors play the role of facilitators who meet the needs of the development of tourist attractions, or as the largest contributor of funds for the construction and operation of tourist attractions. Investors as well as local communities in the tourist attraction also play the role of implementers who implement the policies that have been made by the Village Government. In fact, investors are also accelerators who play a role in thinking about steps to achieve common targets through the positions they hold as field management.

The collaboration of stakeholders is due to the tourism potential owned by the village but the lack of funds owned by the village to realize Banteran village into a tourist village. This is called collaborative governance or partnership of government institutions in terms of public services. Although each stakeholder has a clear role, the synergy between them sometimes does not go well. Based on the results of the study, it shows that the stakeholder collaboration (Ansell & Gash, 2008) has encountered obstacles. This is evidenced by the decrease in the number of visitors and unmaintained facilities so that it reflects management and promotion problems in the management of this tourism (Nieves-Pavón et al., 2024). This problem reflects a lack of coordination and communication between stakeholders, as well as uncertainty in tourism management and promotion strategies.

Figure 4. Tourism Visitor Data in 2023

Source: Research Data (2024)

The lack of synergy between stakeholders such as the village government, investors, and the local community can hinder the development of the Asih Swargaloka Embung Embankment Tourism. Village governments, investors, and local communities must work more closely together in managing and promoting this tourism (Liu & Cold, 2024). Good cooperation will allow for a more effective division of responsibilities and resources. This can be realized through the formation of a team or committee involving all related parties, with the aim of improving coordination and communication in tourism management (Berliandaldo et al., 2021; Khomzi et al., 2020; Silalahi, 2011).

Repairing and maintaining existing facilities is an important step to attract visitors. In addition, the addition of new rides and activities can provide a new experience for visitors and increase the attractiveness of tourist attractions (Rifansyah & Sihombing, 2022; Sudarwan et al., 2021). Innovation in the form of special activities or events can also be an attraction in itself. For example, holding festivals or seasonal events that attract the attention of visitors (Prompayuk & Chairattananon, 2016; Surugiu & Surugiu, 2015). Promotional efforts need to be increased through various media, including social media, official websites, and cooperation with travel agents (Amdan et al., 2022; Setyowardhani et al., 2019). Creating attractive promotional packages for local and out-of-region visitors can be an effective strategy to increase the number of visitors. In addition, the use of influencers or community leaders who have a large following on social media can help increase the visibility of this tour (Mandjusri & Irfan, 2018).

Capacity building training for tourism village managers is needed to improve their abilities in management, village potential exploration, and digital marketing (Ingkadijaya & Bilqis, 2020). A participatory approach that involves the community in the management and development of tourism will increase the community's sense of ownership and responsibility for the success of this tourism (Bobsuni & Ma'ruf, 2021). Strategy adjustments are also needed to ensure development goals are achieved. Maintaining good communication between the village government, investors, and the community will create strong synergies and ensure that all parties are working towards the same goal (Subejo et al., 2021). With the implementation of a comprehensive development strategy and good synergy between all stakeholders, Embung Tanggul Asih Swargaloka Tourism can again attract visitors and become a sustainable source of income for Banteran Village. Training and empowerment of tourism village managers, facility improvements, and effective promotion will be the key to the success of this tourism development. Good synergy between stakeholders is not only important for the development of the current Asih Swargaloka Embung Tanggul Tourism, but also for the sustainability of this tourist attraction in the future. By working together effectively, stakeholders can ensure that this tourism continues to grow, attract visitors, and provide economic benefits to the village community.

6. CONCLUSION

The importance of stakeholder synergy in project development, including in the context of tourism development, is something that needs to be considered. Synergy allows for more effective achievement of common goals, optimization of resources, increased innovation, better risk management, and long-term project sustainability. In addition, synergy also increases community participation, transparency, and accountability, as well as strengthens the competitiveness of tourist destinations. The decrease in the number of visitors and the condition of unmaintained facilities at Wisata Embung Tanggul Asih Swargaloka reflect problems in management and promotion. The lack of synergy between stakeholders consisting of village governments, investors, and local communities is the main factor that hinders the development of this tourism. To overcome this problem, closer cooperation

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between the three parties is needed. With the implementation of a comprehensive development strategy and good synergy between all stakeholders, Embung Tanggul Asih Swargaloka Tourism can again attract visitors and become a sustainable source of income for Banteran Village.

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